

**EFFECTS OF FOREIGN PORTFOLIO INVESTMENT ON THE FINANCIAL
MARKETS IN NIGERIA**

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Abstract

This study examines the effects of foreign portfolio investment on the financial markets performance in Nigeria. It specifically employed time series data for the period 2009-2018 sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria (C.B.N) bulletin and World Bank analyzed with Error Correction Model (ECM), Ordinary least square and correlation techniques to determine whether FPI stimulate or destabilize economic performance of Nigeria. Secondary data were employed to arrive at the result of the findings. The value of 0.65 indicates good linear regression with 42% of the variation in the dependent variable revealed by the coefficient of determination (R^2), while the remaining 58% was due to other factors not presumed in the variation model. The value of Durbin-Watson in this study is 1.77 indicate good formulation of the portfolio investments. The result above revealed that the intercept (constant) of the equation is 5.69. This value of 0.04 is positive and statistically significant since P-value is less than 0.05 level of significant, indicating Foreign Inflow will increase by beta 2.05 and t of 2.24. Since the result shows that the null hypothesis was rejected it implied that foreign portfolio investments have significant impact on financial markets in Nigeria. Whereas, Since the Sig value is 0.20 (which is greater than .05), it mean the values are not significant, indicating Foreign Outflow will decrease by beta 1.44 and t of 1.42. On this basis of these findings, the study concluded that FPI poises threat to Nigeria economy, partly because it more amenable to sudden withdrawing.